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Metabolic shifts in the aging myeloid compartment.

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We describe here observed enrichment of hexokinases *HK1* and *HK2*, *PFKFK4*, pyruvate kinase *PKM*, and aldolase *ALDOA* in newborn monocytes. *LDHA* and *GAPDH* enrichment in newborn monocytes likely more related to cell death differences